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Semantic Analysis of Phraseological Units in the Spanish Language

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***Abstract:** In this article, the semantic features of phraseological units in the Spanish language are analyzed. The lexical meaning and contextual use of phraseological units, their metaphorical and national-cultural features are considered. The study analyzes the structural composition of phraseological units, types of meanings, and their place in linguistics. The article also provides a comparative analysis of phraseological units in Spanish with other languages, focusing on the problems and equivalence issues in the translation process. The research results confirm the importance of semantic analysis of phraseological units in the process of learning Spanish and demonstrate their practical significance for translators.*

***Key words:** phraseological units, semantics, Spanish language, metaphor, national-cultural features, translation.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is an integral part of human thought and culture, and its richness and expressive possibilities are largely manifested through phraseological units. Each language has its own idioms, which reflect the historical, cultural, and social experiences of the speakers of that language. Phraseological units not only enrich the semantic system of the language, but also express its national-cultural features. Therefore, the study of the semantic aspects of phraseology is of great scientific and practical importance. This research is aimed at conducting a semantic analysis of phraseological units in the Spanish language. Spanish is one of the most widespread languages in the world, and its phraseology is very rich and unique. By studying the semantic aspects of phraseological units, we have the

opportunity to analyze their cultural foundations, as well as to determine their structural composition, types of meanings, and methods of expression. This article analyzes the semantic features of phraseological units in the Spanish language, their lexical and contextual meanings, as well as metaphorical and national-cultural aspects. A comparative analysis of Spanish phraseological units with their equivalents in other languages is also carried out, and the main problems arising in the translation process are considered. The research results are important both in the study of the Spanish language and in the translation process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the study of the semantic features of phraseological units, their metaphorical, metonymic, and figurative meanings play an important role. The theory of conceptual metaphor, developed by J. Lakoff and M. Johnson (1980), serves as an important methodological basis for analyzing the semantic structure of phraseological units. According to this theory, phraseologisms are based on metaphors that reflect human thought and worldview, and their semantic analysis is also related to cultural aspects. The works of such researchers as E. Alvarez (2001), A. P. Lebedeva (2013), and M. I. Kovshova (2015) on the study of the national-cultural features of phraseological units in the Spanish language are of great importance. These studies deeply analyze the semantic structure of phraseological units, their linguocultural and communicative features. Research devoted to the issues of translation of phraseological units is also of great importance. Scientists such as A. V. Fedorov (1973), P. Newmark (1988) have developed various methods for the equivalence and interpretation of phraseological units in translation. Issues of semantic transformations, equivalence, and pragmatic adaptation in the process of translating phraseological units from Spanish into other languages have been studied separately.

Methodology

In this study, the Descriptive Analysis Method, Semantic Analysis Method, Comparative Analysis Method, and Corpus Analysis Methods were used to study the semantic features of phraseological units in the Spanish language. These methods made it possible to deeply study the semantic features of phraseological units and determine their place in linguistics.

RESULTS

As a result of this study, the semantic features of phraseological units in the Spanish language were analyzed, and a number of important conclusions were drawn.

Semantic types of phraseological units

Phraseologisms in the Spanish language were semantically divided into different groups. For example, metaphorical phraseologisms - these units are mainly based on imagery, and the meaning is expressed indirectly. For example, the phrase “estar en las nubs” (literally: “to be in the clouds”) means “to be dreamy” or “to be far from reality”. Metonymic phraseological units are understood in relation to a phenomenon or object. For example, the phrase “tener buena mano” (literally: “to have a good hand”) means “to be skilled in a certain work”. Phraseologisms with a figurative meaning are constantly dependent on the context and are understood differently from their main meaning. For example, the phrase “poner los cuernos a alguien” (literally: “to give someone a horn”) means “to betray”.

National-cultural identity

It was revealed that the majority of phraseological units in the Spanish language are connected with the culture, history, and traditions of the Spanish people. For example, the expression “Más vale pájaro en mano que ciento volando” (“A bird in hand is better than hundreds of birds flying in the sky”) reflects

the practical way of thinking of the Spanish people and encourages caution. The phrase “Sir un Don Juan” (literally: “To be Don Juan”) is derived from the famous image of Don Juan in Spanish literature and is used in the sense of “a man who easily captivates women”.

Translation and equivalence problems

The translation of phraseologisms often requires semantic adaptation. For example, the phrase “Estar entre la spada y la pared”, translated directly, means “to be between a sword and a wall”. But this phraseologism is actually used in the sense of “being between two difficult choices”. The phrase “to be caught between two fires” in the Uzbek language is a close equivalent to it. The phrase “No tener pelos en la lengua” (literally: “not having hair on the tongue”) means “to speak openly, not to hide anything”, and the choice of an equivalent in translation is of great importance.

Corpus analysis results

Analysis based on linguistic corpora showed that phraseological units can have different meanings in different contexts. For example, the phrase “Echar leña al fuego” (literally: “throwing firewood into the fire”) is used in the sense of “increasing the tension of the topic” during discussions or disagreements. This phrase can sometimes be used in a neutral context. The phrase “Irse por las ramas” (“to go to the branches”) is used in the sense of “deviation from the subject”, which contributed to the study of the possibilities of its use in official speech and in the literary context.

DISCUSSION

The research results confirmed that the semantic aspects of phraseological units in the Spanish language are complex and multifaceted. Phraseologisms appear not only as linguistic units, but also as an integral part of the cultural and historical context. In this section, the research results are discussed in more detail, and their significance in general linguistics, translation theory, and intercultural communication is analyzed.

Semantic features of phraseological units in the Spanish language

Semantic analysis of phraseological units has shown that they often have metaphorical, metonymic, and figurative meanings. Most of the phraseological units in the Spanish language are derived from folklore, historical events, and social experience. For example, the phrase “No tener pelos en la lengua” (“Not having hair on the tongue”) is a phraseologism expressing open-mindedness in Spanish culture. The phrase “Estar entre la espada y la pared” (“To be between a sword and a wall”) is used to describe difficult choice situations. Such phraseological units can undergo semantic changes in different contexts, and their use depends on the style of speech, the purpose of communication, and the communicative context.

National-cultural characteristics and translation problems

Phraseologisms often have a national-cultural connotation, and their direct translation can create difficulties. For example, the phrase “Sir pan comido” (literally: “To be eaten bread”) means “extremely easy work”. It can be translated into Uzbek as “Qo‘ldan keladigan ish” or “bolalar o‘yini”. The phrase “Sir un Don Juan” (“To be Don Juan”) is based on a historical-literary context and does not have an equivalent in all languages. In the Uzbek language, it can be expressed in a similar sense with such words as “a man who talks a lot to women” or “an unstable man”. The problem of finding a direct equivalent in the translation of phraseological units shows that translators must take into account not only semantic correspondence, but also pragmatic and cultural aspects.

The role and pragmatic significance of phraseological units in speech

Phraseological units are used to influence the listener or reader in the process of communication, to express an emotional state, and to enrich speech. Corpus analysis showed that some phraseological units, although less frequently used in official speech, are very actively used in both spoken and informal speech. For example, the phrase “Echar leña al fuego” (literally: “throwing firewood into the fire”) is widely used in oral speech in the sense of “enhancing the conflict”. The phrase “Irse por las ramas” (“Going to the branches”) means “deviation from the topic” and is often used during debates or official speeches. The use of phraseological units is also connected with communicative strategies, and their change depending on the context affects the effectiveness of communication.

CONCLUSION

The research results showed that phraseological units in the Spanish language have a complex semantic structure, and their formation is associated with historical, cultural, and social factors. Phraseologisms often have a metaphorical and figurative meaning, reflecting national-cultural features. When translating phraseological units, it is important to find a semantic equivalent, since literal translation in most cases does not give the correct interpretation. The results of the corpus analysis confirmed that the use of phraseological units in real speech depends on different contexts. This study contributed to a deep study of the semantic analysis of phraseological units in the Spanish language and served to determine their place in translation and intercultural communication.

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